

PUBLIC ATTITUDE TOWARD FEMALE BODY PORTRAYAL IN THE INTERNET IN ASABA, DELTA STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: This study examined the public attitudes toward female body portrayal in the Internet. This study aimed to understand the level of public awareness, public exposure, public consumption, and public attitudes regarding female body portrayal on the Internet. The study, which was anchored on Cultivation Theory, adopted a cross-sectional research design with focus group discussions. The study analyzed emanating qualitative data using the thematic approach. Findings show a significant level of public awareness of female body portrayal and characterization on the internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria and that the level of exposure to them is high and even higher among internet users who registered for internet platforms with a higher tendency to contain such online content. The level of public consumption of female body portrayal on the internet in the study area is high for only members of the public who have sufficient access to it and those who find it interesting and low among members of the public who find it offensive or have limited exposure to it, while the public attitude toward these contents is more negative than positive. This study recommends that internet users and influencers should promote diversity in female body representation across online platforms while encouraging ethical content creation that respects women's dignity.

Key Words: Body positivity; female body characterization; female body image comparisons; Ideal female body; Objectification of women; Women's sexualization.

Introduction

Female body portrayal is the practice of identifying female physical endowment in a public space for public admiration. Itire, Chukwudebe, Ogunlade, Ukwenya, Johnson, and Uwejigbo (2022), define body portrayal as a multidimensional concept that encompasses perceptual, cognitive-affective, and behavioral domains. In other words, it is the way that people view themselves and their own bodies and this may be sometimes in relation to another person. According to Shahi, Tripathi, and Koli (2020), body image is a psychological term that describes how a person looks and feels about his or her own body, as well as how they feel about other people's

bodies. The bulk of civilizations are obsessed with beauty and good looks. In recent years, body image and characterization have gained increasing attention in academic research, although their rising prominence can be traced back nearly four decades, (Yang, Wang, Ting & Yang 2020).

Over the years, the world has been experiencing technological changes, and the Internet, which is the hub of modern information and communication technologies, has transformed human activities. The internet is a medium that has a significant impact on many areas of human activity. The availability of information and freedom to communicate with others are much greater than ever (Ijeh 2008). In network society, the internet contributes to the emergence and development of citizen initiatives for people, especially females, to display their bodies (Looft 2017). Initiatives that begin online are later transferred beyond the ‘virtual’ sphere, even though they are coordinated through it. The Internet has enabled an increasing number of women to participate and engage. It forms the foundation of a new virtual society, existing on its own terms, with unique institutions, norms, culture, cultural elites and power structures. This platform allows women to shape and express their identity globally, fostering the creation of new forms of social interaction and expanding their influence in various spheres of life, (Lawan, Samuel, Barnabas, Sunday & Magaji 2017).

In essence, the study helps identify prevailing attitudes and trends regarding female body image, which can influence social norms and cultural standards. It helps in identifying and challenging harmful stereotypes and biases related to female bodies, promoting a more inclusive and diverse representation, (Shahi et al 2022). Studying public attitudes toward female body characterization on the internet is essential for fostering a healthier, more inclusive society and mitigating the negative impacts of unrealistic and harmful body standards.

Statement of the Problem

The portrayal and characterization of the female body in the Internet has become increasingly pervasive and has therefore attracted some level of research. For example, Yao, Niu and Sun (2021) in a study on body image comparisons on social networking sites and Chinese female college students’ restrained eating report that online representations often promote unrealistic beauty standards and have been linked to body dissatisfaction, negative self-esteem and mental health issues, particularly among women. In another study on the effect of social media on body image, self-esteem, and social appearance anxiety among young adults, Sharma (2024) point out that social media has a big impact on how young females see their bodies because of the heavy exposure to idealized and unrealistic body ideals, which are frequently depicted by influencers and celebrities and cause body dissatisfaction, poor self-perception, low self-esteem, and an increase in social appearance anxiety. Perloff (2014) studied social media effects on young women’s body image concerns and reports that there is heavy online presence of young women whose reliance on social media influences their perceptions of body image and body image disturbance, which predispose them to individual vulnerability characteristics, body dissatisfaction, and eating disorders. Phillips and Halder (2019), on their part focused on social media and the imposition of female body characterization in Tobago and found out that while there is a correlation between social media and negative body image, there is no evidence to prove that social media have direct impact on one’s body image.

The above studies and many others provide useful insights into female body portrayal and characterization on the Internet and demonstrate how they affect society. However, nothing much has been documented on how the public feels about the phenomenon in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. What are the levels of public awareness of, exposure to, and consumption of female body portrayal contents on the Internet in Asaba, Delta State? What is

the attitude of the public toward such online content in the study area? These questions and the absence of ready answers indicate obvious gaps in the knowledge that this study on the public attitude toward female body portrayal on the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria attempts to fill.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. examine the level of public awareness of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria;
2. find out the stage of public exposure of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria;
3. determine the level of public consumption of female body portrayal content in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, and
4. Examine public attitudes toward female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of public awareness of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of public exposure of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of public consumption of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?
4. What is the public attitude toward female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria?

Delimitation of the study

The study is delimited to public awareness of, exposure to, consumption of, and attitude toward female body portrayal in the Internet. The study is also limited to Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, for a 3-month period from July to September 2024.

Literature Review

Level of Public Awareness of Female Body Portrayal on the Internet

The internet has significantly increased awareness of female body characterization by expanding the visibility of body portrayals, fostering body positivity movements, enhancing media literacy, and providing platforms for diverse voices (Looft 2017). While these developments have led to important discussions and shifts in societal attitudes, ongoing efforts are necessary to address the challenges associated with unrealistic beauty standards and promote inclusive and realistic representations of female bodies. The internet has played a pivotal role in increasing awareness of female body characterization by expanding visibility, fostering body positivity movements, enhancing media literacy, and providing platforms for diverse voices. (Yao et al 2021). While this increased awareness has led to important discussions and shifts in societal attitudes, ongoing efforts are needed to address the challenges and continue promoting inclusive and realistic representations of female bodies (Iteire et al 2022). The internet's role in shaping and reflecting these conversations underscores its impact on both public perception and individual self-image, (Cao, Hu, Wang, & Wu 2023).

The pervasive influence of social media on female body image is increasingly evident as young women navigate platforms saturated with idealized representations of beauty. This phenomenon contributes to a significant shift in self-perception and body satisfaction, often leading to heightened body dissatisfaction and anxiety. Studies have indicated that frequent exposure to curated images, predominantly featuring slender,

flawless bodies, intensifies feelings of inadequacy and social comparison among young female users. As Sharma (2024) highlights, these interactions can diminish self-esteem and amplify social appearance anxiety, creating a reinforcing cycle of negative body image and unhealthy behaviors (Ijeh 2017; Boursier, Gioia & Griffiths 2020).

In addition, the review of gender norms and social media reveals a lack of cohesive research on these impacts among adolescent girls, indicating the need for targeted studies that explore these complex interactions further (Rodgers & Rousseau 2022). Ultimately, understanding the relationship between social media and body image is crucial for developing effective interventions that promote healthy self-perception among young women, (Peloff 2014).

Level of Public Exposure to Female Body Portrayal on the Internet

A channel of exposure to female body portrayal is the internet, as it provides a platform for female gender to create public awareness. People are becoming more informed these days because of the internet. Contents shared on the internet can reach an unimaginable number of people across the globe in seconds (Ijeh 2008; Yao et al 2022). There is an argument that the level of public awareness of female body portrayal in this internet age is unprecedented. The internet is a platform that has a significant impact on many areas of human activity, especially physical representation. This is the reason Looft (2017) argues that the information of any type is not hidden from people because the internet has great potential to create public awareness of human activities within the shortest possible time. Regarding female body portrayal, the public is significantly aware of the trends in the presentation of the female body on the internet because of its polarization. The internet provides continuous connectivity at any time or place. Internet connection enhances the availability of textual, pictorial, and video content on female body characterization for the public (Ijeh 2017; Lawan et al 2017).

An unprecedented number of users visit the Internet daily and have significant access to its contents (Ijeh 2008; Cao et al 2023). This has led to significant knowledge about female body portrayal around the world. Females are considered to be among the easily influenced users of the Internet, and their public awareness is high (Perloff 2014). The public is also very aware of the pressure this gender faces on the internet in order to showcase their body builds. One form of entertainment is social networks, which include Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and Twitter. Facebook makes it possible to connect and keep in touch with friends, chat with them, and add photographs. It also fosters modern online advertising. Internet users have become both creators and consumers of information, perspectives, and ideas about female body characterization. This dynamic has opened avenues for the public to observe how these representations are portrayed and amplified online, (Milutinovic, Zelic & Nedeljkovic, 2014).

Level of Public Consumption of Female body portrayal on the Internet

The consumption level of internet content is overwhelming. The majority of people accessing the internet do so because of their interest in consuming specific content (Ijeh 2008). According to Cao et al (2023), the majority of young adults aged 16–40 years predominantly spend so much time on the internet on a daily basis. One of the most prominent types of content consumed by these demographics is related to female sexuality. Both men and women engage with and consume representations of female body characterization. For Rupesh, Rakesh, Winnier, Kaimal, John, & Prasannan (2014), the reason for female body portrayal content consumption among internet users is the fact that males are more attracted to female sexual disposition, while the female is interested in adopting a replica of the ideal female body portrayal they consume online. This of course, increases the

volume of content relating to female body portrayal available on the internet as well as the consumption rate. There is an argument that most women use the internet to express their public appreciation of their body, thereby creating specific body portrayals. (Iteire et. al. 2022),

Currently, the female body displayed on social media represents the ideal appearance of girls by establishing a body template, displaying their good figure, and promoting social competition among themselves. For example, some women wear more revealing clothes and intentionally post photos of their good figures on social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram because of their high interest in views and content sharing (Cao et al 2023).

Public Attitude toward Female body portrayal on the Internet

Female body portrayals have attracted public debate and discussion. Since the internet revolution has created a great opportunity for people to publicize their images on the internet for free and for the admiration of the public, persons have spoken out to criticize these activities. Some people have developed a negative attitude toward the manner in which the female body portrayal in the internet as a way for dishonoring female virtue among unknown audiences (Phillips & Halder 2019). However, another part of the female population can actually have a positive impact on the public by displaying themselves on social media as a way of disapproving some influencers. Using the Internet to express their sports and female identity, international female athletes have challenged these arguments in the literature on self-representations (Cao et al 2023). The public can take athletes as the standard of health when they display their identity as athletes and show in the Internet how they exercise, eat work, and rest in order to maintain a healthy lifestyle. As a means of improving media literacy, it is suggested that individuals acquire the ability to think independently and critically and acquire knowledge of how to distinguish the authenticity and quality of various online sources such as female body portrayal. It has also been described as important to increase awareness of the importance of preserving privacy given that previous network cheating has become increasingly popular, and body images are highly personal information likely to be misused by others (Perloff 2014).

For all sorts of images, viewers realize that in contemporary society, not only the perfect is appreciated. However, regarding body image issues in the Internet, the risk of privacy disclosure is high. Cao et al (2023) states that the possibility of leaking address information or other seemingly trivial private messages can be decoded from photos when female users post personal pictures online with a wide range of internet surfers, both familiar and unfamiliar, posing a threat to their personal security in such situations.

Further, the attitude of some persons toward female body portrayal is the issue of body anxiety, which is another defect that causes people to feel anxious when they see others who are more beautiful than they are, resulting in a craze for competing with other who are thinner or more attractive. It is often the case that sarcastic remarks or defamatory remarks lead to a dramatic decline in women's self-confidence, which has unexpected counterproductive consequences, despite initial intentions to embrace themselves and show self-love, (Phillips & Halder 2019). By simply pondering what body images should be posted and what should be avoided, or by deliberately checking the content of the pictures that will be uploaded in the near future to ensure that no personal information will be disclosed, the public attitude suggests that one can prevent the occurrence of negative intention for female body portrayal on the internet (Cao et al 2023).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Cultivation Theory, which was developed by George Gerbner in the 1960s, (Gerbner & Gross, 1976). The theory posits that long-term exposure to media messages can shape individual

perceptions of social reality, influencing their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. Cultivation theory is a communication and sociological framework that holds that long-term exposure to media shapes how consumers perceive the world and conduct themselves in life, (Riddle, 2010). In the context of this study, the theory provides a lens for understanding the potential influence of the internet on attitudes and behaviors related to female body portrayal online (Obert-Hong, 2019). The theory states that individuals who are heavy users of internet platforms may be more likely to perceive female body portrayal because of its high presence.

In addition to cultivation analysis, which examined how the media (especially television) shaped consumers' perceptions of reality, the Cultural Indicators Project also analyzed two other related spheres. For instance, television, like the Internet, offers auditory and visual messages simultaneously and therefore does not require much literacy. Furthermore, access to television (just like the internet) is almost universal, and the engaging narrative style that television programming generally employs (which is possible on the internet) readily captures viewers' attention (West & Turner 2010). The second assumption is that television influences society's manner of relating and thinking (Settle, 2018). It is said that the consciousness cultivated by television involves the standards of judgment as well as the facts of life and stabilizes societal patterns and induces resistance to change (Gerbner & Gross 1972; Gerbner 1998). It has also been argued that the effects of television may be limited by other social factors (Gerbner et al 1978). Television is here identified as part of a larger sociocultural system such that the aggregation of its effects in a certain direction is considered substantially more critical than the singular effect of a certain programme at a particular point in time (Gerbner, Gross, Morgan & Signorielli 1980). These points indicate that while watching television per se might not automatically lead to certain behaviors, watching television over time can significantly influence how we perceive the world (West & Turner 2014). As noted earlier, the internet appears to be a channel of mass communication today that shares the attributes of simultaneous presentation of audiovisual content with a real-time advantage over television. Therefore, this study applied the above-mentioned assumptions of television to the Internet.

From the above scholarly postulations on cultivation theory, it is clear that the constant and repetitive depiction of idealized female forms online can shape societal views and individual self-concepts, often leading to a distorted and narrow understanding of beauty. As the Internet continues to evolve, it is crucial to critically assess the content consumed and its potential impact on human perceptions and beliefs. The above theoretical framework provides enough basis to examine the levels of public awareness of, exposure to, consumption of, and attitude toward female body portrayal on the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional research design with a focus group discussion. A focus group is ideal for exploring complex social phenomena and capturing diverse perspectives on sensitive topics such as female body portrayal on the internet. The population of the study covers adults in Asaba, Delta State, and was estimated to be 205,600, as projected from the 2006 population census figures (<https://www.citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/>). The study adopted a sample size of 12 purposively selected from the 21 to 40 years age bracket based on the submission by Guest, Namey, and McKenna (2017) that 6–12 participants per group is typical for generating a good balance of perspectives without overwhelming the discussion. The study adopted a discussion guide as instrument for data collection and conducted focus group discussions via a dedicated WhatsApp group where discussants freely aired their opinions on issues raised via voice notes, texts and shared internet materials to buttress their points over a one week period. The study

adopted the thematic analysis approach for data analysis where responses from discussants were considered from the basis of points of convergence and divergence to arrive at consensus.

Data Analysis

The demographic composition of the discussants in this study shows equal numbers of male and female (6 each) and equal numbers from each age bracket (21-25 years =3; 26-30 years =3; 31-35 years =3 and 35-40 years =3) as a result of the purpose sampling to ensure gender and age bracket balance in the sample. The distribution of discussants by educational level shows that the majority of them (7 = 58.33%) had tertiary education, while the remaining 5 (41.67%) had secondary school education, as a result of the purposive sampling of participants with appreciable level of education.

Level of public awareness of female body portrayal in the Internet

The discussion on the level of public awareness regarding female body portrayal revealed that all participants claimed that they had smartphones and frequently browsed the internet. In the words of **Discussant 1**: “individuals are aware of female body characterization on the internet due to the prevalence of smart phone use”. **Discussant 2** noted that “people use smartphones for almost everything because there are numerous things available on the Internet”. On his part, **Discussant 4** declared that “Some people, particularly young people spend an average of 6 hours on the internet because the content that appeals or receives the most views and readership is related to sexuality, and female body portrayal makes up the majority of the content people search for on the internet”. Arising from this point of absolute convergence of views, this study concludes that the level of public awareness of female body portrayal on the internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria is high.

Level of public exposure of female body portrayal in the Internet

The views of the discussants in this regard are varied. While they all agree that every user of the Internet has the opportunity to be exposed to female body portrayal contents online, two points of divergence were expressed. Some discussants believed that the opportunity was unequal, as registration with social media and other user restricted internet platforms that contain more female portrayals provide greater exposure. Another point of divergence was that differences in the frequency of surfing the internet based on interest, occupation, lifestyle, and access to internet connectivity, access to electricity to power gadgets, and possession of functional gadgets significantly affect individual levels of exposure. In the words of **Discussant 3**, “Individuals often access websites and social media platforms that feature and promote female body categorization, either directly or implicitly.” These sites are diverse and may include social media platforms, fitness websites, fashion blogs, and entertainment or celebrity gossip websites that require prior registration. **Discussant 7** strongly indicated that content connected to female body traits do not wait for registrations on special websites as they frequently appear while people are using their phones, particularly when browsing social media, exploring the internet or consuming digital contents in the form of unsolicited advertisements, promotional posts and suggested contents. **Discussant 6** sheds light on how many Internet platforms employ algorithms to propose comparable content to what their users have already viewed, which is quite bothersome because some of these feminine body portrayals appear unexpectedly. Arising from the foregoing thematic data analysis, this study found consensus in the fact that the level of public exposure to female body portrayal on the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria is high but higher among internet users who registered for internet platforms with a higher tendency to contain such online content.

Level of public consumption of female body portrayal in the Internet

Qualitative data emanating from this area of interest in the study indicate an agreement among all participants that consumption of female body portrayal is based on a number of factors, such as level of exposure, tastes, moral beliefs, and peer influence. For example, **Discussant 9** stated that "many people share female body portrayal photos and videos, particularly after they have toned up." This shows that these people are proud of their accomplishments, but they place high value on their physical appearance". She added that "for instance on a Saturday morning, what welcome you as soon as your internet is connected are the various pictures and videos of female who just left the gym or are currently in the gym doing one form of exercise or another especially those from Squash Club or Steve Kesh Stadium both based in Asaba in a manner that suggests that there are more females than males in the gym on stadium these days'. As a result, peer pressure from their female folk lures many females to view these Saturday gym posts". **Discussant 8** reported that female friends share more of this type of content, such as gym programs or diet-related posts and also added that the statistics could be in the percentage of females (65%) while males (35%). **Discussant 12** confirmed that these internet posts are popular on Instagram, where people visit to see a lot of posts about female-related beauty routines, eating habits, and workouts that constantly focus on acquiring a specific female physical shape. **Discussants 2, 4, and 10** stated that they frequently encountered content that focused on female body portrayal, either purposefully or unintentionally. While some people do not deliberately seek content about female body types, they acknowledge that such content is impossible to avoid due to its presence in popular media. On their part, **Discussants 1 and 11** stated that people frequently consume content linked to female body portrayal, notably in the realms of fashion and fitness. They reported a desire for information that promotes body positivity, but acknowledged the challenge of locating such content in a sea of media that reinforces specific beauty norms. **Discussant 10 stated** that some people consciously avoid content that focuses on female body characteristics; thus, they likely spend little time on it, despite the fact that even unrelated content frequently contains such depictions, making it unavoidable in small doses. Arising from the analysis above, this study concludes that the level of public consumption of female body portrayal on the internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria is high for only members of the public who have sufficient access to it and those who find it interesting and low among members of the public who find it offensive or have limited exposure to it.

Public attitudes toward female body portrayal in the Internet

Data available on this objective of the study indicate both positive and negative attitudes. The positive attitude was expressed by **Discussants 5, 6, 7 and 8** who claimed that the body positivity movement had a substantial impact on the use of female body portrayal on the internet as influencers, corporations and public figures are increasingly welcoming and promoting diverse body types, supporting self-acceptance regardless of size, shape or appearance. On the other hand, **Discussant 5** expressed the belief that there has been a rising awareness of the unrealistic portrayal of female bodies on such platforms, leading to initiatives for body positivity and body neutrality. **Discussants 1, 2, 3, and 4** agreed that female body portrayal frequently revolves around restricted and unattainable beauty norms, which can lead to damaging comparisons. Many public debates about female bodies center on physical appearance rather than personal accomplishments or characteristics, which contribute to objectification. Participants expressed dissatisfaction with unrealistic images of female bodies in the media and online, implying that such representations can contribute to unfavorable societal opinions and pressures. **Discussants 9, 10, 11 and 12** expressed the view that a large amount of online female body portrayal focuses

on women's sexualization. This is especially visible on social media platforms and in online marketing, where women's bodies are frequently shown in a way that values look over other attributes or achievements. The participants expressed concern about the objectification of women online, which is consistent with the larger issue of female bodies being reduced to objects of desire rather than individuals with depth and autonomy.

Discussion of Findings

Given the level of public awareness of female body characterization on the Internet, the majority of the participants totally agreed that people significantly use smartphones on a daily basis, and their quest for the usage of smartphones has increased the awareness level of female body characterization in the Internet. This implies that there is public knowledge about what female body characterization is all about among younger demographics. The study is in relation to existing studies as the Internet has opened avenues for the public to observe how female body presentations are portrayed and amplified online (Milutinovic, Zelic, & Nedeljkovic, 2014). In another study by Cao et al (2023), the internet is visited by an unprecedented number of users, and they are caught up by having significant access to internet posts and content, especially relating to female body characterization.

On the level of public exposure to female body portrayal in the Internet, the findings indicate that the majority of the participants visit websites and other internet platforms where female body characterization is often displayed both willingly and unwillingly because many of such contents appear in a variety of unsolicited formats, including advertisements, posts, and suggested content. This study is in agreement with an existing study by Cao et al (2023). The internet is visited by an unprecedented number of users, and they are caught up by having significant access to internet posts and content. Females are among the easily influential users of the internet, and their public awareness is high.

Regarding the level of consumption of content relating to female body characterization in the Internet, the study revealed that many people, especially younger demographics, consume content relating to female body characterization in the Internet because of the way the imposter presents these content to influence their viewers. However, some people do not deliberately seek out content about female body types; they acknowledge that such content is impossible to avoid due to its presence in popular media. This study collaborates with Rupesh, Rakesh, Winnier, Kaimal, John, & Prasannan (2014), who argued that the reason for female body consumption among internet users is the fact that males are more attracted to female sexual disposition, while females are interested in adopting a replica of the female body characterization they consume online.

In respect to public attitudes toward female body characterization in the Internet, the results indicated that many public debates about the female body's center on physical appearance rather than personal accomplishments or characteristics, which contributes to objectification. Therefore, there is general dissatisfaction with unrealistic images of female bodies in the media and online, implying that these representations can contribute to unfavorable societal opinions and pressures. The majority of the participants expressed concern about the objectification of women online, which is consistent with the larger issue of female bodies being reduced to objects of desire rather than individuals with depth and autonomy. This study collaborates with an existing study that stated that the public attitude about female body characteristics on the Internet should be judged by gatekeepers on what should be posted and what should be avoided, or by deliberately checking the content of the pictures that will be uploaded in the near future to ensure that no personal information will be disclosed. The

public attitude shows that one can prevent the occurrence of negative intention for female body characterization on the internet (Cao et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is a significant level of public awareness of female body portrayal and characterization in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria. However, while the level of exposure to female body portrayal in the Internet in the study area is high, it is even higher among internet users who registered for internet platforms with a higher tendency to contain such online content. The level of public consumption of female body portrayal in the Internet in Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria, is high for only members of the public who have sufficient access to it and those who find it interesting and low among members of the public who find it offensive or have limited exposure to it, while the public attitude toward these contents is more negative than positive.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, the study recommends the following:

- ❖ Internet users and influencers should promote diversity in female body representation across online platforms.
- ❖ Internet users and influencers encourage ethical content creation that respects women's dignity.
- ❖ Internet users and influencers should reach audiences focusing on media literacy to critically evaluate the portrayals of women.
- ❖ Internet users and influencers should implement regulations to monitor and guide commercial practices involving women's images.
- ❖ Internet users and influencers should shift their societal focus toward valuing women's uniqueness, character, and strengths rather than focusing on physical appearance alone.

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